

STUDY OF ENGINE PERFORMANCE ON GASOLINE AND BIOETHANOL-CONTAINING FUEL

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Bioethanol and methanol obtained from the processing of organic waste and agricultural lands can compete with petroleum fuels used in internal combustion engines. The use of bioethanol and methanol as additives to petroleum fuels, in particular motor gasoline, requires thorough and in-depth research to obtain scientifically sound results. In some cases, bioethanol and methanol are used as additives to motor gasoline and diesel fuels. A number of research papers indicate the prospects of using biological fuels in internal combustion engines [4-9].

The authors indicate the use of biofuels in different concentrations in the composition of petroleum fuels. And the improvement of traction-economic and environmental indicators is indicated. Bioethanol is an alternative type of fuel for powering internal combustion engines, which has an increased environmental friendliness class. A derivative of plant components and agricultural crops, bioethanol demonstrates good performance as an economical fuel for cars, but it also has disadvantages [4-9].

One of the features of the development of the modern world is the increased attention of the world community to the problems of efficient use of energy resources, the introduction of energy saving technologies and the search for renewable energy sources [4-9]. Biofuels have priority among renewable energy sources [4].

The main components of biofuels by origin are alcohols obtained from food or feed raw materials: sugar cane, sugar beet and some other agricultural crops. Based on their basic physical and chemical properties, biological fuels can be used in operating conditions as a substitute for gasoline. Another important drawback is its low calorific value. When bioethanol is burned, 37-40% less thermal energy is released compared to traditional types of automobile fuel. This significantly limits the power characteristics of the engine [5-8].

High solar radiation and good productivity of gray soils contribute to obtaining high yields of fruits and vegetables at low costs. With additional processing of these wastes using an incorporated method, a significant amount of bioethanol can be obtained [8-10].

However, to date, biological fuels have not become widespread for two main reasons: the higher cost of bioethanol compared to fuel oil and the lack of technical or economic advantages to compensate for this high cost. The aim of the study is to assess the impact of biological fuels on the performance characteristics and changes in the main indicators of power plants. Comparison of the results of experimental and theoretical studies on changes in operational indicators, as well as the construction of dependencies of indicators [8-10].

To confirm the possibility of using the resulting mixture as motor fuel, experimental studies of a carburetor engine were conducted. During the operational studies, a mixture of automobile gasoline fuel for a car with a carburetor engine and 5%, 10% and 15% concentration of ethanol

was used (Table 2). The study of the properties of standard fuel and mixtures of "motor gasoline + bioethanol" was carried out in accordance with the existing research methodology [11-12].

The experimental study consists of testing a car engine running on motor gasoline and a mixture of gasoline and bioethanol. The research examined the mixture by its physical and chemical properties, closer to the properties of fuel. But some of its physical properties, for example, density and viscosity were slightly less than similar properties of motor gasoline. 5%, 10% and 15% concentration of the mixture were examined. Solutions of motor gasoline with bioethanol in various concentrations were studied: 5, 10, and 15%. Motor gasoline with bioethanol forms a solution containing water due to the bioethanol solution. Therefore, increasing the concentration of bioethanol solution in gasoline leads to an increase in water content.

Thus, based on the conducted research, it was shown that mixtures of solutions from 5% to 15% can be used as additives to gasoline under the given climatic conditions. Bioethanol contains emulsions that provide phase stability when forming a mixture of motor gasoline and bioethanol. The use of bioethanol as an additive to motor gasoline allows to reduce harmful emissions to the environment and can serve to meet the need for fuel and energy resources. A mixture of motor gasoline and bioethanol forms a solution containing water due to the bioethanol solution.

When conducting research on the fuel mixture of motor gasoline + bioethanol, attention should be paid to the content of water formation in the mixture. Therefore, during operational tests of internal combustion engines running on a fuel mixture containing bioethanol, it is necessary to determine the optimal concentration of the additive. Increasing the concentration of bioethanol solution in gasoline leads to an increase in water content.